

The Coupling Constant Series and Graviton Propagation – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework of the 8T and in particular the first two representation of the coupling constant primordial equation, i.e. Net variations and spin, it is possible to derive an insight about the nature of propagation of the graviton. Due to its spin feature, 8-theory predict a short ranged propagation, similar to the propagation of the strong interaction, which have only one term in the coupling series as well.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Since according to modern theories of physics, the graviton particle has spin two, we can use the second representation of the coupling constant equation, i.e. spin representation using the prime critical line:

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (2.1)$$

Recall that even amount of primes combined will never form a prime but an even number. Up to this point, everything on this assay was covered on previous papers and in the thesis of the 8T. The main point than is that even amount of variations vanish in this framework, and therefore the graviton will not propagate as spin one particle all across the matrix. The propagation would be like the propagation of the strong interaction, as both have only one term in the coupling constants series.

$$[2N(g) + 2] \rightarrow 2N(g) \quad (2.11)$$

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1)$$

That could come to an agreement with the fact that it was not detected up to this point. There is the implicit assumption that spin one will propagate all across due to its prime number feature, and even amount of variation is associated with local propagations on the matrix.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)